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KCNK1 and KCNK2 are disrupted in epilepsy.

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We used whole transcriptome technologies to discover molecules whose function is likely to contribute to pathology in the seizure disorder epilepsy. We describe here perturbed expression of potassium channels encoded by the genes *KCNK1* and *KCNK2* in the brains of humans with epilepsy.